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The relationship between perceived stress and physiological parameters in competitive alpine skiers

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship between perceived stress and physiological parameters among alpine skiers. The subjects selected for the study had previously participated in either the Khelo India Winter Games or the All India Inter-University Winter Sports. Their ages ranged from 20 to 30 years old, with a total of fifty participants (N=50) included in the research.

Methodology: For this study, the physiological parameters measured included body mass index (BMI), resting heart rate, and vital capacity and were assessed using the weight/height ratio, a heart rate monitor, and a dry spirometer, respectively. Perceived stress was evaluated using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), developed by Sheldon Cohen *et al.*

Result and Analysis: Descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation analysis were employed to interpret the data. The results indicated a significant relationship between body mass index & vital capacity, vital capacity & resting heart rate & resting heart rate and perceived stress among alpine skiers. However, no significant relationship was found between body mass index & resting heart rate, body mass index & perceived stress and vital capacity & perceived stress among the alpine skiers.

Conclusion: The study concludes that skiers with higher vital capacity tend to have lower perceived stress levels, and vice versa. The study further concluded that a higher BMI is associated with a higher vital capacity, and vice versa and a higher resting heart rate values is associated with more perceived stress, and vice versa among alpine skiers.

Keywords: Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), Body mass index (BMI), Resting heart rate, and Vital capacity

1. Introduction

Athletes participating in winter sports are a particularly important population to research in this area. Sportspeople who compete in alpine skiing, snowboarding, ice hockey, biathlons, ski jumping, and speed skating sometimes deal with a special set of pressures that are uncommon in other sports (Kiemle-Gabbay & Lavallee, 2017) [5]. Extreme low temperatures, hypoxic circumstances at high elevations, complex and fast-paced motor coordination demands, and high-risk situations are a few examples of these stressors. Their mental burden is further increased by psychological difficulties such as severe competition pressure, lengthy travel obligations, and protracted separation from known social support networks during practice or competition (Norcross *et al.*, 2015) [8].

These emotional and environmental difficulties are a part of winter sports athletes' everyday lives and careers; they are not isolated incidents. As a result, their effectiveness is constantly affected by how well they handle these mounting demands. In addition to training their bodies for strength, endurance, and accuracy, athletes in these sports also need to control their mental health in order to be motivated, focused, emotionally stable, and mentally clear. Winter sports players are a pertinent and interesting group to study the connection between perceived psychological stress and physiological function because of this intricate mind-body interaction (Martín-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2024) [6, 7]. When psychological stress is present, changes in hunger, digestion, and energy metabolism may have an indirect impact on BMI. Stress hormones like cortisol are known to interfere with regular hunger cues and encourage fat retention, especially around the abdomen. Stress-induced changes in body composition can lead to inferior performance and even disordered eating patterns in athletes, particularly those competing in performance categories that require leanness (Martín-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2024) [6, 7].

Stress frequently causes shallow, fast breathing, or hyperventilation, which lowers oxygen exchange efficiency and eventually lowers vital capacity. Since aerobic power and endurance are key components of many winter sports, a decrease in critical capacity might jeopardize the oxygen delivery to working muscles, which will ultimately limit performance and raise the danger of exhaustion (González-Alonso & Calbet, 2003) [2]. RHR is a great way to find underlying psychological or physiological strain in athletes because it is non-invasive, simple to test, and extremely sensitive to internal stress (Purvis *et al.*, 2010) [10].

2. Methodology

The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship between perceived stress and physiological parameters among alpine skiers. The subjects selected for the study had previously participated in either the Khelo India Winter Games or the All India Inter-University Winter Sports. Their ages ranged from 20 to 30 years old, with a total of fifty participants (N=50) included in the research. Prior consent was taken from subjects before administering the tests and the purpose of the study was explained to all the subjects. For this study, the physiological parameters measured included body

mass index (BMI), resting heart rate, and vital capacity and were assessed using the weight/height ratio, a heart rate monitor, and a dry spirometer, respectively. The formula used to calculate body mass index is:

$$\text{BMI} = \text{weight (kg)} / (\text{height (m)})^2.$$

Perceived stress was evaluated using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), developed by Sheldon Cohen *et al.*

3. Result & Analysis

The complete interpretation of data collected using descriptive and relationship statistics is illustrated in tables 1 & 2 respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Body Mass Index	22.19	2.17	50
Vital Capacity	4.20	0.64	50
Resting Heart Rate	63.42	4.57	50
Perceived Stress	24.44	2.32	50

The mean values and standard deviation values for the body mass index, vital capacity, resting heart rate and perceived stress obtained in the alpine skier subjects is 22.19±2.17, 4.2±0.64, 63.42±4.57 & 24.44±2.32 respectively.

Table 2: Correlations

Variable	N	Body Mass Index	Vital Capacity	Resting Heart Rate	Perceived Stress
Body Mass Index	50	.1	0.381**	-0.093	-0.169
Vital Capacity	50		1	-.106	-0.369**
Resting Heart Rate	50			1	0.492**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

- There is positive correlation between body mass index and vital capacity $r(50) = 0.381$, $p=0.01$ among competitive alpine skiers.
- There is no correlation between body mass index and resting heart rate and perceived stress among competitive alpine skiers.
- There is no correlation between vital capacity and resting heart among competitive alpine skiers.
- There is negative correlation between vital capacity and perceived stress $r(50) = -0.369$, $p=0.01$ among competitive alpine skiers.
- There is positive correlation between resting heart rate and perceived stress $r(50) = 0.492$, $p=0.01$ among competitive alpine skiers.

Fig 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Selected Physiological and Psychological Parameters (BMI, Vital Capacity, Resting Heart Rate, and Perceived Stress)

4. Discussion

The results indicated a significant relationship between body mass index & vital capacity, vital capacity & resting heart rate & resting heart rate and perceived stress among alpine

skiers. However, no significant relationship was found between body mass index & resting heart rate, body mass index & perceived stress and vital capacity & perceived stress among the alpine skiers. The environment of winter sports

may present particular stressors, such as exposure to bitter cold, intense physical demands, and pressure to compete during peak seasons, all of which may intensify stress reactions. By hindering recuperation, decreasing sleep quality, and raising vulnerability to injury or illness, elevated stress and its physiological correlates may have a detrimental impact on performance (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2017) ^[3]. The effects of increased perceived stress in sports are significant and wide-ranging. Furthermore, persistent or uncontrolled stress can lower motivation, make it more difficult to create goals, and raise the dropout rate among athletes (Hrozanova, *et al.*, 2021) ^[4]. The assessment of perceived stress in combination with important physiological indicators provides a potent framework for both scientific research and real-world intervention in high-performance, high-stress settings such as winter sports (Pelz, 2024) ^[9]. We may learn a great deal about how stress may affect or reflect physical preparedness, resilience, and recovery capacity in elite winter athletes by determining the relationship between perceived stress and metrics like body mass index (BMI), vital capacity, and resting heart rate (RHR).

Winter sports athletes often practice and compete in challenging conditions, which exacerbates mental and physical challenges. The cold temperature might cause respiratory problems, increased energy needs, and muscle rigidity (D'Amato *et al.*, 2018) ^[1]. High altitudes, which are common in sports like alpine racing and ski mountaineering, can cause hypoxia, vertigo, and impaired oxygen absorption. When these physiological pressures are combined with social isolation, technical difficulties, performance pressure, and injury anxiety, an extraordinarily stressful environment is created. Physiological monitoring is essential since winter athletes may not always report their stress levels due to stigma or ignorance. If perceived stress is not identified or managed, it can lead to long-term health issues, stall recovery, or eventually decrease performance (Stults-Kolehmainen & Bartholomew, 2012) ^[11].

5. Conclusions

Following conclusions are drawn:

1. A positive correlation was found between body mass index (BMI) and vital capacity among competitive alpine skiers. This means that a higher BMI is associated with a higher vital capacity, and vice versa.
2. There is no correlation between body mass index, resting heart rate, and perceived stress among competitive alpine skiers. Additionally, no correlation exists between vital capacity and resting heart rate in this group.
3. A negative correlation was observed between vital capacity and perceived stress among competitive alpine skiers. This indicates that skiers with higher vital capacity tend to have lower perceived stress levels, and vice versa.
4. Lastly, a positive correlation was identified between resting heart rate values and perceived stress among competitive alpine skiers. This suggests that a higher resting heart rate values is associated with greater perceived stress, and vice versa.

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